

Work-Related Quality of Life of Social Studies Teachers a Pursuing Advanced Education

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ABSTRACT: This study describes the work-related quality of life of Social Studies teachers pursuing advanced education, particularly master's degree. Using a descriptive research design, 37 respondents who are identified as Social Studies teachers currently enrolled in the degree of Master of Arts in Education major in Social Studies answered a survey questionnaire developed by the researchers. The data was interpreted through a 4-point Likert Scale and revealed that the respondents agree that they have a good work-related quality of life ($M = 3.21$). Ranked highest is Job and Career Satisfaction ($M = 3.76$ while slightly lower is Home-Work Interface ($M = 2.96$). Finding suggests that school administrators and policy-makers should adopt steps to strengthened their work-life balance to ensure the work-related quality of life of Social Studies pursuing advanced education is in excellent condition to avoid physical, mental, social, and financial burdens.

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KEYWORDS:

job and career satisfaction, stress at work, working conditions, general well-being, control at work, home-work interface

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INTRODUCTION

Throughout across generations, the teaching profession in the Philippines is highly regarded as a noble profession, as teachers serve as role models to the community. However, it must also be regarded that teaching is not only the end of their career. Teachers also endeavor to go beyond the classroom instruction and pursue advanced education in furtherance of their technical and pedagogical competencies. As stated in the study of Panuelos and Pili (2025), teachers are the anchors of societal development for a well-developed educational system who also need to metamorphose from one mold to another.

Many Social Studies teachers pursue advanced degrees for purposes of promotion, professional development, self-satisfaction and knowledge acquisition despite the workload in their respective institutions. It is also a reality that they have other assigned tasks, aside from their teaching assignments. Such multifaceted nature of their work significantly disturbs their work-life balance and their quality of life as it impacts not only their physical bodies but also their mental and social well-being. Much more, their satisfaction on their profession is affected.

The need of prioritizing the quality of life of Social Studies teachers is important as it impacts their profession and their personal life. According to Rao et. al., (2013) as cited by Panuelos and Pili (2025), quality of work life refers to the employees' satisfactions with various aspect of work life, such as financial, working conditions and skills. When a teacher does not feel satisfied with his/her quality of life in the workplace, there is a possibility that such discomfort may result to stress and burnout, leading to further medical implications. Or worst, they abandon their profession at the cost of their instinct for self-survival (Brooks, 2005, as cited by Abbasi, 2017).

In the study of Abbasi (2017), the quality of working life mirrors the person's perception of the organization and can impact and influence the job satisfaction of an employee. If the working environment is favorable for the practice of the profession, it leads to greater satisfaction among workers and can lower levels of burn-out and it minimizes the number of professionals who abandon

their profession (Barandino, 2019). Affirming this, Kumar (2016), concludes that the alignment between work environment emphasizes the importance of motivation and job satisfaction of organizational productivity.

Also, productivity is affected by sickness and disease brought by stress and burnout, according to Haw et.al. (2020). Migraine poses a substantial impact on the personal and economic burden on many working age individuals. Thus, the effort of pursuing advanced education among Social Studies teachers should be an engaging professional journey as it is in furtherance of the profession and as a worthwhile contribution in providing the learners and the institution the needed expertise in both content and pedagogy. Physical, mental and social health should, at all times, be looked into to ensure optimal productivity and general well-being among teachers.

Thus, this study aims at describing the quality of life of Social Studies teachers in their workplace during their pursuance of advanced education. The results of this study will provide insights on how Social Studies teachers who are pursuing advanced education cope with the challenges brought by work, life and professional endeavors in their professional journey and advancement.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive analysis as it aimed at describing the work-related quality of life among Social Studies Teachers who are pursuing advanced education. This is the appropriate methodology, as it was focused on quantifying opinions and allows identification of patterns within a definite population (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

The data was gathered through survey questionnaire developed by the researchers which was administered to identified respondents who are currently pursuing advanced education at Mariano Marcos State University – Graduate School for two academic years (2023-2024 & 2024-2025). The data was interpreted through a 4-point Likert Scale (4- Strongly Agree, 3- Agree, 2- Disagree, 1- Strongly Disagree) which includes the following criteria: Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS), Stress at Work (SAW), Working Conditions (WC), General Well-being (GWB), Control at Work (CAW) and Home-Work Interface (HWI).

Purposive sampling was used to ensure that all participants are strictly Social Studies teachers who are pursuing advanced education. This approach was employed as it is deemed suitable for the inclusion of the respondents who are the primary respondents of this study. Specifically, the respondents are Social Studies teachers who are identified as enrolled in the Master's degree at the Mariano Marcos State University – Graduate School.

All respondents voluntarily participated in the data gathering. They were briefed of the study's purpose, the confidentiality of their responses and was informed that their participation would not, by all means, affect their academic standing. Ethical guidelines including informed consent, data storage and protection and disposal were strictly followed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the data and interprets the work-related quality of life of Social Studies teachers pursuing advanced education. It aims to provide a qualitative description of the quantitative data obtain from the survey questionnaires administered to the respondents to be able to interpret the Likert scale applied in the study. The results shall reflect their present work-related quality of life in pursuing advanced education.

Table 1. Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel a sense of pride when I apply my graduate studies to my Social Studies lessons.	3.95	Strongly Agree
2. My school administration actively encourages my professional growth through advanced education.	3.78	Strongly Agree
3. I am satisfied with the career advancement opportunities my master's/doctorate will provide.	3.95	Strongly Agree
4. I feel that my current teaching job allows me to use my full potential as an educator.	3.68	Strongly Agree
5. I am happy with the balance between my teaching accomplishments and my academic progress.	3.54	Strongly Agree
6. The subject matter I teach aligns well with my advanced research interests.	3.78	Strongly Agree
7. I feel valued as an intellectual by my colleagues while I pursue my degree.	3.73	Strongly Agree
8. My pursuit of advanced education makes me feel more competent in the classroom.	3.84	Strongly Agree
9. I am satisfied with the training and support provided by my current institution.	3.54	Strongly Agree

10. Overall, I am proud of the career path I have chosen as a Social Studies professional. 3.78 Strongly Agree

Overall Job and Career Satisfaction **3.76** **Strongly Agree**

As shown in *Table 1*, Social Studies teachers are satisfied with their job and career, showing that they take pride in the profession that they have chosen and is willing to pursue professional development by pursuing advanced education in the field of specialization. Based from the data above, the pursuance of advanced education made them a more accomplished teacher in both personal and professional aspects. This implies that pursuing advanced education helps them improve their academic and intellectual competence in Social Studies, which is in line with the findings of Bulilan (2022). However, the training and support provided by their institution is a significant factor in their pursuance to advanced education. Thus, it is suggested that teachers should be provided with more opportunities for training and extended support in their endeavor towards professional development.

The balance between teaching accomplishment and academic progress also scored the lowest among the other dimensions, although it is within the stratum of their strong agreement. This is attuned to the finding of Gore, et al. (2017) which suggests that teachers' satisfactions of their accomplishments are usually connected with their pursuit of academic progress. Thus, they should be encouraged to pursue advanced education to be able to attain self-actualization in their field of specialization. Thus, it is affirmative that motivation for training and support should be extended to teachers of Social Studies to help them attain professional fulfilment and academic competence.

Moreover, these findings have also big implications to the teachers' self-esteem which is integral to the psychological needs of an individual. Thus, when a person feels that his/her achievement is motivated and recognized, it builds their confidence to perform better and take pride in their actions. The support that educational institution provides is a determining factor of the willingness and engagement of its teachers in their pursuance of advanced education. To address these, Farleni et. al. (2024) suggested that policy makers should require professional teachers to pursue advanced studies as part of their professional qualifications to boosts their competence not only locally but also globally.

Table 2. Stress at Work (SAW)

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I often feel overwhelmed by the simultaneous demands of grading papers and writing my own research.	3.27	Strongly Agree
2. I experience physical exhaustion due to the lack of rest between teaching and attending classes.	3.22	Agree
3. I worry about my performance in graduate school while I am at my workplace.	3.19	Agree
4. The pressure to maintain high teaching standards while studying is mentally draining.	3.24	Agree
5. I find it difficult to meet school deadlines because of my university requirements.	2.76	Agree
6. I feel "burnt out" by the end of the work week due to my evening or weekend classes.	3.03	Agree
7. My physical health has been negatively affected by the stress of my dual responsibilities.	2.68	Agree
8. I feel constant pressure to prove that my studies are not distracting me from my students.	2.81	Agree
9. I lose sleep worrying about the financial obligations related to my advanced education.	2.92	Agree
10. I find it hard to disconnect from work-related stress even when I am in my graduate classes.	2.81	Agree
Overall Stress at Work	2.99	Agree

Table 2 describes the stressors experienced by Social Studies teachers. Ranked as top stressor is the overwhelming demand of grading papers while writing their research work, resulting in a stressful and mentally draining balance between work and academic life, a finding that is the same with Gudelos, et al. (2025). In addition, they agree that on most points, that physical exhaustion that is brought about by lack of rest, demands in their academic workload and high teaching standards by their supervisors and superiors resulted to burnout, stress, and work-family conflict that may further result into abandonment of the advanced education (Damaske et. al., 2016). Also, they fully agree that the constant thought of their performance or standing, and the financial

expenses in the graduate school added to the psychological burden that further exhaust them which may result to a poor teaching performance, a parallel result with the findings of Ji & Yue (2020).

Considering the physical, mental, and economic constraints experienced by teachers, it is suggested that work-life balance should be strengthened by adopting measures for their professional and personal well-being. While it is true that teaching is a tedious job, it must be noted that there is also a thin line that separates their professional and personal lives. To overcome the stressors experienced by teachers, it is suggested that work-life balance should be strengthened by adopting measures on how to properly manage work requirements and personal activities and engagement. A healthy balance between work and life must be strengthened as it influences and affects job performance meaning, a person works well when he is satisfied with his job and it also improves employee retention (Reed, 2021; Montaña, 2025).

Table 3. Working Conditions (WC)

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My school provides adequate facilities (e.g., Wi-Fi, library) to support my academic research.	2.86	Agree
2. I have a safe and comfortable workspace to prepare my Social Studies materials.	3.11	Agree
3. The physical environment of my school is conducive to productive professional work.	3.14	Agree
4. My teaching schedule is flexible enough to accommodate my university class hours.	3.11	Agree
5. I have access to the necessary technology to conduct both teaching and graduate research.	3.00	Agree
6. My school's location makes it easy to commute to my university or study center.	2.95	Agree
7. The classroom environment allows me to implement new strategies learned in graduate school.	3.32	Strongly Agree
8. I am satisfied with the level of cleanliness and orderliness in my workplace.	3.32	Strongly Agree
9. My school provides a quiet space where I can focus on tasks during my breaks.	3.14	Agree
10. I feel that my workload is distributed fairly compared to teachers not pursuing further studies.	2.95	Agree
Overall Working Conditions	3.09	Agree

The table above shows that among the working conditions needed by Social Studies teachers, ranked as highest is the conduciveness of the work-study environment, this suggests that having a quiet and orderly space can affect teaching productivity and academic performance (Toyinbo, 2023). Also the knowledge learned from the graduate school helps advance and provide new teaching strategies in the conduct of classes, this makes the teacher even more effective in the teaching-learning process affirming the study of Licayan & Arroyo (2025) which stated that teachers enrolled to advanced education is proven to be more effective in their profession.

While physical environment of their institution greatly provides a conducive environment, it is evident from the table above that there is a lack of facilities which would help provide access to wider variety of resources to support their advanced education. According to Limon (2016), lack of facilities negatively affects academic performance. Thus, to address this issue Wi-fi, reading center and library, access to modern technologies and physical facilities should be the top priority of educational institutions as it is the source of knowledge in today's generation. Better academic facilities offers better engagement in the teaching-learning process and greatly helps teachers pursuing advanced education in their research and studies (Nkrumah, 2023).

Table 4. General Well-Being (GWB)

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I feel generally happy with my life as a teacher-scholar.	3.05	Agree
2. I have enough energy left at the end of the day for my family and hobbies.	2.86	Agree
3. My pursuit of advanced education gives me a sense of deep personal fulfillment.	3.65	Strongly Agree

4. I rarely feel depressed or anxious about my current life situation.	2.86	Agree
5. I am able to maintain a healthy lifestyle despite my busy schedule.	2.97	Agree
6. I feel motivated to wake up and go to work every morning.	3.03	Agree
7. My self-esteem has improved since I started my advanced education journey.	3.41	Strongly Agree
8. I have a strong support system of friends and family who understand my dual role.	3.65	Strongly Agree
9. I feel that my life is "in balance" right now despite the academic load.	3.19	Agree
10. I am optimistic about my future as a highly-educated Social Studies professional.	3.68	Strongly Agree
Overall General Well-Being	3.24	Agree

As shown in the table above, Social Studies teacher are highly optimistic about their future in their chosen profession, this is influenced by the support of friends and family and the personal fulfilment they experience and the boosts in self-esteem in pursuing advanced education.

However, optimism is affected by the physical exhaustion by the teachers leaves them unable to cope up with the demands of their family and personal hobbies to which they are unable to maintain a healthy lifestyle. Also, they feel depressed and anxious of their current life situation. A strengthened work-life balance is suggested to address this problem as it will help them manage their personal, professional, and academic activities.

According to Song (2022), well-being among teachers provides advantages because it contributes to the stability of teachers in their profession. Optimism can also help bolster resilience and lessen the occurrence of stressors (Aldbyani, et. al., 2025). Thus, by the positive view of the Social Studies teachers in their profession, it helps them realize their full potential and general well-being.

Table 5. Control at Work (CAW)

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I have the freedom to choose which Social Studies topics to emphasize in my class.	3.03	Strongly Agree
2. My supervisors listen to my suggestions based on my advanced academic knowledge.	3.08	Agree
3. I am involved in the curriculum planning process at my school.	3.00	Agree
4. I feel I have a say in how my teaching schedule is structured to fit my studies.	2.97	Agree
5. I can independently decide on the best teaching methods for my students.	3.57	Strongly Agree
6. My opinions are respected during faculty meetings and department sessions.	3.24	Agree
7. I have control over the pace at which I complete my daily teaching tasks.	3.46	Strongly Agree
8. I feel empowered to introduce innovative Social Studies projects in my department.	3.41	Strongly Agree
9. My school administration trusts my professional judgment without constant supervision.	3.22	Agree
10. I am able to influence the policies that affect my work-life balance.	3.08	Agree
Overall Control at Work	3.21	Agree

The scores at the control at work is significantly positive where teachers strongly agree that they have independence to decide the best teaching methods for their students, this affirms the discussion on Table 3 that they were able to apply what they learned from the graduate school in their day-to-day teaching setting; Social Studies teachers are also in control of the pace on which they complete their daily tasks. Also, they can work independently without constant supervision from their administrators and being

able to introduce innovative project in their departments. This independence and confidence from their co-teachers allow them to apply their new knowledge acquired in pursuing advanced education, this makes them a better teacher, a competent educator, and an independent facilitator.

Scheduling should be considered however, to be able for the teachers to utilized properly their vacant time and to provide them more opportunities of a continuous professional endeavour during the pendency of their work. According to Noor et. al., (2025), proper timetable management teachers' instructional performance and productivity improve when they are involved in scheduling and workload distribution.

Table 6. Home-Work Interface (HIW)

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My school is supportive when I need time off for university exams or seminars.	3.16	Agree
2. I am able to leave my work "at school" to focus on my graduate studies at home.	2.65	Agree
3. My family is supportive of the time I spend away for my classes and research.	3.70	Strongly Agree
4. I rarely have to sacrifice my personal life to fulfill my teaching duties.	2.73	Agree
5. My advanced education has a positive impact on my family's perception of my career.	3.62	Strongly Agree
6. I can effectively manage my household chores alongside my teaching and studying.	2.97	Agree
7. My school honors my boundaries regarding after-hours work communication.	2.89	Agree
8. I have sufficient time for social activities outside of work and school.	2.84	Agree
9. My income as a teacher is sufficient to cover my basic needs and tuition fees.	2.59	Agree
10. I feel that my career, my education, and my home life are moving forward in harmony.	2.49	Disagree
Overall Home-Work Interface	2.96	Agree

Table 6 presents the home-work interface of Social Studies teachers. It revealed that family and school's support had a positive impact in their perception of their career development. Schools support the teachers through allowing them attend university exams or seminars in pursuant to their advance education through this, teachers can have more time to prepare for their academic exams and advance their professional development. Family's support can enhance their productivity through healthy communication and shared responsibility when overwhelmed by requirements in the graduate school. According to Zhang et. al. (2020), when family roles are delegated, the experience they acquire from these roles can be utilized for their personal development. On the other hand, if there is a conflict in the family, it drastically affects the performance on an individual which leads to poor performance (Moreira et. al., 2023). Therefore, the role of the school and family in supporting the teachers are important as it helps them prepare physically, mentally, and socially in their advanced education and research. (Uy & Callo, 2023).

Table 7. Overall Work-Related Quality of Life (WRQL)

Dimension	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Job and Career Satisfaction (JCS)	3.76	Strongly Agree
2. Stress at Work (SAW)	2.99	Agree
3. Working Conditions (WC)	3.09	Agree
4. General Well-Being (GWB)	3.24	Agree
5. Control at Work (CAW)	3.21	Agree
6. Home-Work Interface (HWI)	2.96	Agree
Overall Work-Related Quality of Life	3.21	Agree

Overall, the findings revealed that Social Studies teachers agree that they have a good work-related quality of life pursuing advanced education. This indicates that teachers of the said field while experiencing difficulties and challenges such as financial expenses, burdens of submission of subject requirements in the graduate school and work-life balance, are still able to have a balanced work-life and is optimistic of the career they had pursued. This optimism helps them advance their career and personal growth while strengthening their credentials at the same time (Gavín-Chocano, et. al., 2024).

Overall, Social Studies teachers pursuing advanced education whose work-related quality of life is promising translate that they take pride in their career development however, strengthening scheduling, balancing work, family, and personal life is still a factor to improve is recommended to avoid burn-outs, stress and anxiety towards their endeavour in the advanced education.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that Social Studies teachers pursuing advanced education agrees that they have a good work-related quality of life. The support of their school, family and friends, and their self-worth helps them face the challenges brought by advanced studies.

Scheduling, unhealthy lifestyle, burn-out, stress, anxiety, financial burden, lack of facilities and the pressure on submission of requirements are factors that affect their work-related quality of life therefore, it should be emphasized that policy-makers and school administrators should collaborate in helping teachers in their pursuit of personal and professional development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the study, the following are recommended (a) teachers should be involved in crafting schedules especially those pursuing advanced education to help them maximize their work and studies during their pendency, (b) teachers' work-life balance should be strengthened and monitored to avoid poor teaching performance brought by physical and mental exhaustion, (c) it must also ensured that teachers are satisfied with their career and job by providing them adequate resources i.e. salary and career opportunities to help them in their financial obligations at school and at home; and (d) there should also be seminars and workshops related to stress management and mental healthcare to allow teachers to be physically and mentally healthy during their pursuit of advanced education while engaged in the teaching profession.

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